

and chlorpyrifos were also effective. Yields of azolla treated with the three insecticides were three times greater than those of the untreated check. Bactospeine provided some insect control and caused significant yield differences com-

pared to the check.

To reduce the cost of insecticide application, it is recommended that azolla stock culture be sprayed 2-3 days before it is transferred to the propagation field. Another application is neces-

sary 7 days later. Because azolla cultivation should begin after transplanting rice, insecticide applications also affect rice insects. *h*

Efficacies of new granular and spray insecticides on rice pests

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During rainy and winter seasons of 1981-82 four granular and six spray insecticide formulations were field tested for control of seasonal pests on varieties Jaya and Tella Hamsa. Treatments were in a randomized block design and three replications.

Granular formulations of endosulfan, thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate, bendio-

carb, and phorate were applied at 1.0 and 0.5 kg ai/ha and compared with maximum protection and an untreated control. Spray formulations of fenvalerate, isofenphos, bendiocarb, carbosulfan, thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate, and phosalone were applied at 0.5 and 0.35 kg ai/ha and compared with an untreated check.

Insecticides were applied at 30, 50, and 90 days after transplanting (DT) after pretreatment insect counts were recorded. Counts were made by dividing the plot into four quadrats and randomly selecting six hills from each quadrat.

Tillers and deadhearts (DH) were counted to determine percent DH; panicle bearing tillers and whiteheads (WH) were counted to determine percent WH; and leaves and leaf folder-damaged leaves (LFDL) were counted for percent LFDL. Grain yields were calculated after eliminating two border rows from all sides.

During both seasons, yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* was the predominant pest. Leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* caused 20% leaf damage on the rainy season crop.

Thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate was

Efficacies of granular and spray insecticide formulations, Warangal, India, 1981-82.^a

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Rainy season				Winter season			
		Yellow stem borer deadhearts (%)		Leaffolder damaged leaves (%)		Yellow stem borer deadhearts (%)			Yield (t/ha)
		50 DT	90 DT	60 DT		30 DT	50 DT	90 DT	
<i>Granular formulation</i>									
Endosulfan	1.0	13.4 ab	8.1 a	16.7 c	2.7 d	12.7 bc	6.5 b	9.9 ab	4.2 b
-do-	0.5	13.7 a	9.6 a	16.8 bc	3.3 c	17.8 b	9.5 a	8.1 bcd	3.4 c
Evisect	1.0	3.0 e	0.8 d	3.0 f	4.4 a	8.0 cd	0.3 d	3.5 c	5.3 a
-do-	0.5	3.7 e	1.3 d	4.1 f	4.2ab	10.4 cd	0.7 d	4.4 e	5.0 a
Bendiocarb	1.0	9.0 c	8.5 a	11.9 d	3.3 c	17.8 b	9.7 a	11.0 a	2.0 cd
-do-	0.5	11.4 b	7.9 a	16.1 c	2.6 d	23.7 a	7.6 ab	6.9 d	2.3 e
Phorate	1.0	9.0 c	5.7 b	6.8 e	3.0 cd	6.0 d	0.4 d	7.3 cd	5.2 a
Maximum protection treatment ^a	1.0	6.2 d	3.8 c	5.9 e	3.8 b	6.3 d	2.8 c	2.6 f	5.1 a
Untreated control A	-	14.1 a	8.7 a	20.1 a	2.1 e	27.2 a	7.7 ab	9.3 abc	2.2 e
Untreated control B	-	14.1 a	9.6 a	19.2 ab	1.7 e	27.0a	8.6 ab	9.5 abc	2.7 de
<i>Spray formulation</i>									
Fenvalerate	0.3	15.4 ab	7.9 bc	1.9 fg	2.8 b	7.9 cde	8.3 de	8.7 bcde	4.3 bc
-do-	0.15	17.8 a	12.7 a	2.5 ef	1.8 ef	12.6 b	17.6 abc	8.0 cde	3.9 d
Isofenphos	0.5	4.1 e	3.6 ef	6.6 c	3.9 a	-	-	-	-
-do-	0.35	9.8 c	5.1 c	8.5 b	2.9 b	-	-	-	-
Bendiocarb	0.5	14.2 b	6.2 cd	2.2 efg	1.8 ef	12.6 bc	14.6 bc	11.0abc	4.1 cd
-do-	0.35	13.8 c	6.4 cd	2.0 g	2.2 cde	13.9 b	14.4 bc	12.6 a	3.9 d
Carbosulfan	0.5	6.5 d	3.1 fg	2.9 e	2.5 bcd	3.7 f	2.7 f	7.4 e	5.0a
-do-	0.35	9.2 c	3.4 fg	0.9 f	3.0 b	8.0 ef	8.9 e	12.1 ab	4.5 b
Evisect	0.5	6.6 d	2.2 g	1.7 g	3.8 a	9.8 bcde	4.3 f	3.7 f	5.1 a
-do-	0.35	6.4 d	2.5 fg	2.8 ef	2.7 bc	8.0 de	6.0 ef	7.8 de	4.5 b
Phosalone	0.5	14.5 b	8.6 b	4.5 d	1.7 ef	12.1 bcd	12.2 cd	10.7 abcd	4.0 cd
Maximum protection treatment ^b		6.5 d	0.8 h	1.9 fg	3.0 b	6.7 ef	9.8 ef	1.7 g	5.1 a
Untreated control		17.6 a	12.6 a	9.9 a	1.5 f	21.6a	21.2a	10.7 abcd	2.9 c

^aIn a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bInvolves seedling root dip with 0.02% chlorpyrifos; carbosulfan application at 1 kg ai/ha, at 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting (DT); and quinalphos spray at 0.3 kg ai/ha, at 75 DT.

most effective against stem borer and leaffolder. Treated plants yielded 4–5 t/ha compared with 1.9–2.5 t/ha for the untreated control. It was most effective in both seasons and at both dosages. Isofenphos (0.5 kg ai/ha) and thiocy-

clam hydrogen oxalate 90 SP successfully reduced yield losses to yellow stem borer and leaffolder (see table). Carbo-sulfan, an analogue of carbofuran, was effective against stem borer and leaf-folder. Fenvalerate, a synthetic pyre-

throid, was effective against leaffolder at reproductive phase of the crop under rainy season conditions. Bendiocarb and phosalone were least effective. ✎

Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot at Tirur, India

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In the Chingleput district of Tamil Nadu, rice is planted continuously, depending on availability of water from lift irrigation wells. Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot was studied in 36 planting dates 10 days apart at Tirur PES. The first planting was 10 May 1980, the last 30 April 1981. Six varieties were evaluated without chemical protection.

Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot at Tirur, India, 1980-81.

Planting date	Damage mean (%)
10-5-1980	8.7
20-5	6.5
30-5	7.8
10-6	6.8
20-6	5.0
30-6	4.4
10-7	16.7
20-7	18.4
30-7	13.2
10-8	10.1
20-8	12.9
30-8	10.9
10-9	13.6
20-9	10.1
30-9	15.4
10-10	20.6
20-10	26.3
30-10	20.6
10-11	14.0
20-11	14.5
30-11	13.6
10-12	15.8
20-12	26.9
30-12	33.3
10-1-1981	32.6
20-1	27.6
30-4	17.4
10-2	18.7
20-2	10.1
2-3	11.2
11-3	12.6
21-3	11.7
31-3	11.3
10-4	14.0
20-4	10.2
30-4	14.4

CD (4.99)

Whorl maggot damage to tillers was assessed 30 days after transplanting (DT).

Whorl maggot damage was less than 10% in May-June plantings, 10–20% in July, August, September, February, March, and April plantings, and above

20% in October, December, and January plantings (see table). Pest damage was significantly less on crops planted on 20 and 30 June, and significantly higher on crops planted 20 December to 20 January. The varieties were equally susceptible. ✎

A new scarabaeid beetle pest of dry-land rice in Bangladesh

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Since 1978 a scarabaeid beetle, *Heteronychus lioderes* Redtenbacher, has

caused severe damage to dryland rice in Noakhali, Chittagong, Comilla, and Mymensingh, and on the islands of Sandwip and Hatiya.

Farmers on Sandwip Island, where the beetle is called *talkora* reported a serious outbreak of the pest during April and May 1980 in aus rice (March-August). Aman (July-December) and boro (November-June) crops have also been attacked during dry periods.

Adult beetles are black and about 16 mm long (Fig. 1). They damage plants

1. Scarabaeid beetles, genus *Heteronychus*, that have damaged dryland rice in Bangladesh.